

ADVANCING RETAIL EFFICIENCY: EVIDENCE FROM CASE STUDIES ON AUTOMATIC REPLENISHMENT SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *This paper examines the efficiency and sustainability impacts of automatic replenishment systems (ARS) in grocery retailing. Based on two large-scale implementations—one in Serbia and one in the Netherlands—the study relies on multi-million-record datasets to assess reductions in out-of-stock (OOS) rates and the added value of managerial overrides. Results show that ARS consistently outperforms manual ordering: the Serbian pilot reduced OOS probability by 63 %, while the Netherlands case case achieved a 91 % automatic order acceptance rate, with only 15 % of manual upward changes preventing OOS. Overall, the evidence confirms ARS as a key driver of “hands-off” supply chains, delivering strong economic gains and measurable environmental benefits.*

Keywords: *Automatic Replenishment Systems, Inventory Management, Stock-outs.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Maintaining high product availability while minimizing excess inventory is a persistent challenge for modern grocery retailers. Stock-outs not only reduce immediate sales but also erode long-term customer loyalty, while overstocks increase waste, costs, and environmental impact (Gruen & Corsten, 2007). Despite decades of operational advances, worldwide studies consistently find out-of-stock (OOS) rates of 7–8 %, leading to lost sales of up to 4% (Aastrup & Kotzab, 2010).

The drivers of these inefficiencies are complex: volatile consumer demand, frequent promotions, large assortments, and store-specific factors such as SKU density or backroom capacity all interact to create uncertainty in ordering and replenishment (Corsten et al. 2002; Ehrenthal & Stolzle, 2013; Avlijas et al. 2015). Traditional manual ordering struggles to incorporate such high-frequency data and is labor intensive, while even IT-supported replenishment can fall short if inventory records are inaccurate or lead times fluctuate (DeHoratius & Raman, 2008).

In response, retailers increasingly deploy automatic replenishment systems (ARS), which integrate perpetual inventory records, point-of-sale data, and time-series forecasts to generate store-SKU level orders automatically. Prior research confirms that ARS can reduce uncertainty, smooth the bullwhip effect, cut labor and waste, and improve on-shelf availability (Angerer, 2006; Avlijas et al. 2021).

Yet many existing studies rely on limited samples, short observation periods, or narrow product categories, leaving open key questions about how ARS performs across diverse product and store risk factors, how often human overrides add real value, and which governance metrics best indicate system maturity and trustworthiness (Syntetos et al. 2009, Van Beuningen, 2018).

The goal of this paper is to address these gaps by systematically evaluating the efficiency and impact of automated store-ordering systems on product availability and sustainability performance. By combining large-scale quantitative analysis with insights on stock-out drivers and managerial interventions, it aims to clarify under which operational and market conditions automation outperforms manual replenishment and to propose key performance indicators (KPIs) that support a progressive transition toward “hands-off” retail supply chains.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Efficient replenishment is central to retail supply-chain performance, as product unavailability leads to lost sales, lower customer loyalty, and higher costs. Studies repeatedly find out-of-stock (OOS) rates of 7–8% in grocery retail, translating into measurable revenue losses (Gruen & Corsten, 2007; Aastrup & Kotzab, 2010). Manual ordering, while adaptable, struggles with volatile demand, frequent promotions, and growing assortments, and is prone to inventory record errors and delayed reactions, which can amplify the bullwhip effect and increase waste (DeHoratius & Raman, 2008).

To address these limitations, automatic replenishment systems (ARS) integrate perpetual inventory records, point-of-sale (POS) data, time-series forecasts, and policy rules to generate store- and SKU-specific daily order proposals (Angerer, 2006; Avlijas et al. 2015). Prior research shows that ARS can increase on-shelf availability and reduce labor and waste, thereby improving both financial performance and environmental sustainability (Avlijas et al. 2021). Empirical evidence also indicates that automation mitigates OOS more effectively than manual methods, even in high-risk contexts such as fast-selling items or promotions, while lowering shrinkage and disposal costs (Avlijas et al. 2021).

However, the literature highlights critical dependencies: the success of ARS relies on data quality, forecast accuracy, and organizational trust. Some studies proposed use of machine learning and artificial intelligence in OOS detection and reduction (Andaur et al. 2021; Bhavikatta, 2025; Xu, 2025). Inaccurate inventory data or incomplete promotional information can trigger unnecessary manual overrides (Syntetos et al., 2016; Kiil et al. 2018). Moreover, many studies remain limited in scope or time horizon, leaving open questions about when human interventions truly add value and how best to measure process maturity.

Based on these insights, the following hypothesis guides this research: H1: Automatic replenishment systems improve product availability compared with manual methods.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a comparative multi-case design to evaluate the efficiency and sustainability implications of automatic replenishment systems (ARS) in grocery retailing. Two large-scale implementations were selected to provide complementary evidence: (1) a Serbian multi-format grocery chain that rolled out ARS across 85 pilot stores and 95 high-volume stock-keeping units (SKUs), and (2) Netherlands' second-largest grocery retailer, which implemented a Forecast & Replenishment (F&R) system across 50 stores and the full assortment. Both contexts offer rich transactional data and well-documented operational processes, making them suitable for assessing ARS performance under differing market conditions.

The analysis combines quantitative and qualitative methods. For each case, detailed store–SKU–day level datasets were compiled, integrating point-of-sale (POS) sales, perpetual inventory records, and automated order proposals. After data cleaning (e.g., removal of weight articles and incomplete records), the Serbian dataset contained approximately 2.3 million observations, while the Netherlands case dataset comprised about 3.94 million.

Logistic and probit regression models were applied to measure the effect of automatic replenishment on out-of-stock (OOS) probability while controlling for sales speed, promotional activity, SKU density, and day-of-week effects. To capture managerial behavior and validate quantitative results, semi-structured interviews were conducted with store managers and replenishment planners, focusing on reasons for manual interventions and perceptions of system trustworthiness.

Finally, key performance indicators (KPIs)—including order acceptance, added value of order adaptations, and process trustworthiness—were defined and tracked to evaluate system maturity and guide recommendations for a phased transition toward fully automated, “hands-off” replenishment. This mixed-methods approach ensures a robust assessment of ARS effectiveness across operational, behavioral, and sustainability dimensions.

4. CASE STUDIES

4.1 Case Study A: Serbian Retail Chain

This case focuses on one of Serbia's largest multi-format grocery retailers, operating over 170 stores nationwide. In 2018 the company implemented an automatic replenishment system (ARS) in 85 pilot stores, initially targeting 95 high-volume SKUs in two sensitive

categories—baby diapers and paper towels—where on-shelf availability is critical for customer satisfaction and brand loyalty (Avlijas et al. 2021).

The ARS combined perpetual inventory (PI) aggregation with time-series forecasting and an (s,S) reorder policy. Daily store-level sales, promotional calendars, and historical demand data were integrated to generate order proposals that were automatically transmitted to the central distribution center. Store managers retained the option to override proposals, but actual interventions occurred in fewer than 5% of cases, indicating a high level of trust in the system's forecasts.

Analysis of approximately 2.3 million SKU–store–day observations revealed a reduction in mean stock-out probability, from 3.72% under manual ordering to 1.38% under ARS. Probit regression confirmed a statistically significant impact of automation even after controlling for sales speed, promotions, and SKU density. Marginal effect calculations showed the strongest improvements for fast-moving SKUs (40% lower OOS probability), promotional items (48% lower), and high SKU-density stores (59% lower).

Beyond availability gains, the retailer realized collateral benefits: labor savings from reduced manual ordering, fewer emergency deliveries, lower shrinkage, and measurable reductions in waste-related disposal costs and greenhouse-gas emissions. The project recouped its initial IT investment in less than 18 months, demonstrating both strong operational efficiency and positive sustainability outcomes.

4.2 Case Study B: West European Grocery Chain

Case B focuses on a 2nd largest grocery retailer in the Netherlands that introduced a Netherlands' second-largest grocery retailer with roughly 19% market share, implemented a Forecast & Replenishment (F&R) automated store ordering (ASO) system across its network to replace largely manual replenishment. The system integrates perpetual inventory, point-of-sale (POS) data, demand factors, and minimum shelf quantities to create daily order proposals, which store managers may accept or adjust before a fixed cut-off (Van Beuningen, 2018).

This case study analyzed ≈ 3.94 million SKU–store–day observations from 50 representative stores covering both perishable and non-perishable categories. Results show that $\approx 91\%$ of order lines were accepted without change, and acceptance remained strong at 87% during seasonal peaks such as Easter—evidence of the system's robust forecasting accuracy.

To assess the value of manual interventions, the research combined manager interviews with logistic regression and counterfactual simulations. Around 76% of all manual changes were linked to predictable triggers such as central promotions, second placements, sudden weather shifts, and inventory corrections. Crucially, only $\approx 15\%$ of

upward changes for non-perishables truly prevented an out-of-stock (OOS), while about 65% of downward changes helped reduce waste in perishables.

Table 1: Key operational metrics

Dimension	Case Study A – Serbia	Case Study B – Netherlands
Market context	One of Serbia’s largest multi-format grocery retailers, >170 stores nationwide	Netherlands’ second-largest grocery retailer, ≈19% market share, >585 stores
System deployed	Automatic Replenishment System (ARS) integrating perpetual inventory, time-series forecasting, and (s,S) reorder policy	Forecast & Replenishment (F&R) Automated Store Ordering (ASO) integrating perpetual inventory, POS data, demand factors, and minimum shelf quantities
Scope of pilot / data analyzed	85 pilot stores; 95 high-volume SKUs in baby diapers and paper towels	50 representative stores; ≈3.94 million SKU–store–day observations across full assortment
Manual intervention rate	<5% of order proposals overridden by managers	≈9% of order lines manually adapted; acceptance remains ≈87% even at seasonal peaks
Measured OOS improvement	Mean stock-out probability fell from 3.72% to 1.38% (≈63% relative reduction)	Only ≈15% of upward changes for non-perishables prevented an OOS; base system kept shelves stocked in ≈85% of cases without intervention
Analytical methods	2.3 million SKU–store–day records; probit regression controlling for sales speed, promotions, and SKU density	Mixed methods: logistic regression, manager interviews, and counterfactual inventory simulations
Main drivers of manual changes	Not the focus; interventions rare due to high system confidence	Central promotions, second placements, sudden weather shifts, inventory corrections, and shelf-presentation motives (≈76% of all changes)
Key benefits beyond OOS	Labor savings, fewer emergency deliveries, reduced shrinkage, lower disposal costs and GHG emissions; IT payback	Labor savings from less review, improved supplier data accuracy, reduced food waste, more consistent supply chain data
Strategic implication	ARS proven to reduce stock-outs and waste; strong case for rapid scaling to additional stores and categories	System already highly accurate; recommend progressive “hands-off” policy using KPIs (process trustworthiness, added value of adaptations, order acceptance)

These findings highlight that most manual interventions do not add measurable value and that the automated system already secures high availability with minimal human input. By tracking process trustworthiness, added value of adaptations, and order acceptance as key performance indicators (KPIs), retailer can progressively advance

toward a “hands-off” replenishment policy, reducing labor requirements, improving supplier data reliability, and cutting food waste, thereby strengthening both operational efficiency and sustainability performance.

The two case studies reveal how ARS deliver consistent benefits across very different retail environments, yet they also illustrate context-specific adaptations. Table 1 summarizes key operational and sustainability metrics for comparison and highlights that both implementations improved on-shelf availability and operational efficiency, but differ in focus.

Serbia targeted a limited assortment and demonstrated large stock-out reductions and rapid financial payback. Netherlands case applied ARS across a broad assortment and revealed that most manual changes were unnecessary, pointing to strong potential for near-full automation. Together, these comparisons support the paper’s hypothesis: H1 confirmed—automatic replenishment improves product availability compared with manual methods.

4. DISCUSSION

The two case studies offer complementary insights into the efficiency and organizational impact of automatic replenishment systems (ARS) in large grocery retail settings. Both demonstrate that algorithm-driven ordering can substantially improve on-shelf availability while reducing labor and waste, yet their contexts reveal different paths and challenges toward full automation.

The Serbian retailer implemented ARS across 85 pilot stores and 95 high-volume SKUs, achieving a 63% reduction in stock-out probability (from 3.72% to 1.38%). Probit regression confirmed significant improvements even when accounting for sales velocity, promotions, and SKU density. Gains were especially pronounced in high-risk contexts—fast movers, promotional items, and dense assortments—underscoring the system’s responsiveness to demand surges.

Netherlands deployment of its Forecast & Replenishment (F&R) system was broader, covering ≈3.94 million SKU–store–day observations across 50 stores and the full assortment. Here, 91% of order lines required no manual change, and even during seasonal peaks acceptance remained strong at 87%. Detailed counterfactual analysis showed that only ~15% of upward changes for non-perishables actually prevented an out-of-stock, while ~65% of downward changes helped reduce waste. Most manual interventions were linked to promotions, second placements, weather, or inventory corrections—factors that can increasingly be integrated into algorithmic forecasts.

Together these findings confirm that automatic replenishment consistently outperforms manual ordering in accuracy, speed, and cost efficiency. They also highlight key enablers

of long-term success: data quality and trust (to minimize inventory mismatches), and continuous system enhancement to capture local events and promotional dynamics. Both cases advocate moving toward a “hands-off” policy, supported by clear KPIs such as order acceptance, added value of adaptations, and process trustworthiness. In sum, these studies demonstrate that with strong data governance and iterative refinement, ARS can sustainably reduce stock-outs and waste while freeing staff for higher-value activities.

5. CONCLUSION

Both case studies demonstrate that automatic replenishment systems (ARS) can substantially improve grocery retail efficiency, service levels, and sustainability. The Serbian retailer’s pilot across 85 stores and 95 key SKUs cut mean stock-out probability by 63%, confirmed by probit regression, and delivered rapid financial returns through higher sales and lower waste and labor costs.

Netherlands case large-scale deployment of its Forecast & Replenishment (F&R) system achieved a 91% order acceptance rate—remaining 87% even during seasonal peaks—while counterfactual analysis showed that only about 15% of upward manual changes for non-perishables prevented out-of-stocks. Roughly 65% of downward changes helped reduce waste, highlighting that the automated process already provides high availability with minimal need for human intervention.

Together, the findings confirm that ARS outperform manual ordering in accuracy, speed, and cost effectiveness. Key enablers of sustained success include data quality, process trustworthiness, and KPI-based monitoring (order acceptance, added value of adaptations). By strengthening these foundations and integrating factors such as promotions and second placements into forecasting, retailers can move confidently toward fully or near-fully automated “hands-off” replenishment, simultaneously enhancing supply-chain resilience, reducing food waste, and improving overall sustainability and profitability.

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